

Voice of the future

Listening to Gen Z on Covid-19, mental health, education, work, and misinformation

26 January 2021

“ This timely report reflects diverse young people's concerns about public health during the pandemic...

It starts an important conversation about whose voice matters when mental wellbeing, employment, and lack of trust in the media are at the top of Gen Z's agenda...

Dr Anna Carlile, Goldsmiths,
University of London

Contents

Forward	3
Introduction	4
Methodology	4
Summary results	6
Mental Health	7
Changes in emotional responses during the pandemic	8
A lack of support	8
The voice of those not heard	8
Education and Employment	9
Where to give back to society	10
The rise of the public health officer	10
Public health education for all	11
Misinformation and the vaccine	12
The challenge of misinformation	13
The most trusted media	13
The vaccine	14
Final thoughts	15
Further research	16
Citations	17

Foreward

Theo Richardson-Gool, CEO of Cov360

Cov360 is a grassroots charity created by a dynamic global team of volunteers to advance public health education. We were happy to collaborate with Debut to gauge how the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted Gen-Z.

The data reveals Gen-Z feels unheard, angry, and anxious. With rising demotivation and depression levels, their voice is a stark warning that this pandemic may manifest in a future mental health crisis.

The participants inspired and affirmed our strategy to embrace pioneering approaches. They agree that misinformation is a serious challenge and that we need strategies to combat misinformation and identify news sources that are trustworthy.

We believe Gen Z want greater purpose and agency. The results demonstrate this generation is empathetic and openminded. They want to generate tools that connect with their peers and promote youth-engagement in public health education. Ultimately to improve wellbeing for the whole-of-society.

Gen -Z emphasised the importance of our charity. Nine of the survey participants have since volunteered and joined our team as trailblazers representing the voice of the future.

The report identified a clear need for further research and investment to help Gen -Z adapt to a rapidly changing environment with the complex challenges that will have an enormous bearing on their future. To address their concerns and compliment their work, wellbeing experts at work are needed, and more public health education essential.

Avantika Vaishnav, Marketing Manager, Debut

In this survey, conducted by Debut and Cov360, we asked students and graduates questions regarding the pandemic across the areas of mental health, education and employment, media coverage and the vaccine.

The Gen Z respondents indicated a general decline in mental health during the pandemic. Moreover, 49% of respondents believe they did not have access to mental support.

Respondents strongly agreed on the need for public health experts within companies, and a significant majority believe in teaching more public health modules at university. They are known as the generation that actively participates in global issues, so their desire to be prepared for the future should come as no surprise.

Misinformation and vaccine confidence were notable concerns. 78% of the respondents strongly agreed that misinformation is a critical issue. The BBC and LinkedIn were seen as trusted news and social media sources, while some tabloids seem to be less trusted than social media channels. With 54% of the respondents indicating they would take the vaccine, those of Black and Black British heritage have the lowest vaccine confidence level across ethnicities. What we don't know is whether this percentage would increase with greater trust in news outlets.

Key takeaways are that Gen-Z generally feels unheard in the wake of this pandemic. We conclude that the future generation needs engagement to help them adapt to a new world.

Introduction

The pandemic has resulted in a year riddled with challenges. For young people still in education or those who have recently left it, the difficulties of adjusting to a new way of life presents seemingly insurmountable obstacles.

We conducted this survey to understand Gen Z's experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic and their views on key issues. Their responses to a survey on various topics including mental health, education and employment, misinformation and vaccines has revealed important data, highlighting key areas that demand urgent attention.

Public health is a collective enterprise society can attain. This requires governments and policymakers to build recovery frameworks that incorporate all of society's needs.

The Covid-19 pandemic has seen a health crisis affecting all spheres of society with potentially destructive repercussions in political, cultural, and economic spheres. This fallout can significantly impact the wellbeing of younger generations (UNDP).

In the UK, national lockdowns and school closures can affect young people's future career prospects and social distancing regulations have negatively affected their overall wellbeing.

Aside from this, it is important to understand why society's relationship with public health recovery plans resulting from the pandemic is problematic.

Misinformation, which is a scourge on health, has impacted us all, and the respondents rightly highlight this as a critical hurdle to recovery. The depleted trust in social media as well as established media indicates how widespread the infodemic is. Misinformation has exacerbated health communication around critical issues such as vaccination.

Furthermore, as the UK prepares to roll out its vaccination program crucial to attain population immunity it should be noted that we still do not know what percentage of society require a vaccine to achieve this. Immunity against other RNA viruses is high. Measles requires about 95% of the population to be vaccinated, while Polio needs approximately 80% (WHO, 2020).

We asked the respondents about their confidence in the vaccine. Anticipated to be the biggest and most comprehensive immunisation campaign in history, the number of people willing to take the vaccine will reflect the relationship between society, the NHS, and the UK government.

METHODOLOGY

What Generation Z want

The questions for this survey were drafted via consultation with Debut, and finalized via consultation with a small sample from the Gen Z group.

We asked different types of questions. Some questions used a Likert scale with options ranging from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree', including 'unsure', and others used a different response system which are explained in the summary results section. The combined approach allowed us to extract key insights from the data collected.

Who answered

We received 443 valid responses from a diverse group of Debut app users. Most respondents were either current undergraduates or had recently graduated with an undergraduate degree. Others included recent school or college leavers and postgraduates.

Of the 443 respondents, 53% were female, 27% were male, 19% did not provide details, and 1% identified as non-binary. Further, 38% identified as White, 27% did not provide details, 17% as Asian or Asian British, 10% as Black or Black British, 4% as Mixed, and 4% from Other Ethnic Groups.

Of the 269 respondents who provided details of their degrees, 33% studied Legal/Economics/Management, 32% studied STEM, 23% studied Arts and Humanities, and 12% studied Marketing/Psychology.

What we found

Preliminary findings were obtained across three categories: mental health, education and employment, and misinformation. Within each category, we identify some critical demographic differences to highlight areas of concern that warrant further research.

The opportunity exists to cross-tabulate Debut's categorical (nominal) data concerning gender, degree type and ethnicity with the survey responses (ordinal) data. In each of the three sections, we have featured one of these three categories. However, the results are not self-explanatory and as we note in the further research section, a larger sample size of quantitative data and qualitative analysis would provide more substantive data with which to interpret the findings more accurately. For these reasons, we encourage the reader to remain discerning when considering these responses.

Survey timeline

The survey ran from November 27, and ended when the second lockdown in England concluded at 12:01 am on Wednesday, December 2.

"This timely report reflects diverse young people's concerns about public health during the pandemic, pointing towards the need for a much more context-specific and listening-focused approach to building trust in public health education. It starts an important conversation about whose voice matters when mental wellbeing, employment, and lack of trust in the media are at the top of Gen Z's agenda, opening up a range of important questions for further study."

**Dr Anna Carlile, Senior Lecturer in Inclusive education
Head of the Department of Educational Studies,
Goldsmiths, University of London.**

At Livity we've worked creatively with young people across the UK and beyond for 20 years. We have witnessed first-hand the drastic change in their lives throughout the last year.

The first lockdown felt somewhat novel - we saw a lot of young people appreciating the slowing down of life, learning new skills from their bedrooms and focusing on self-development and self-care. 73% were even feeling 'more positive' about their future. Fast forward 10 months and boredom has been overtaken by a genuine fear about their future and sadness at the missed opportunities and rites of passage. This is compounded by a constant media narrative that they are both to blame for the spread and will be the most systematically disadvantaged generation for years to come. As a result, and in support of one of the big topics raised in this report's findings, we're seeing a sharp rise in messaging fatigue and with the vaccine coming into play, the levels of misinformation and mistrust surrounding it. With the only constant being uncertainty, there is a genuine need to equip young people with the facts, the science and some hope that the future may not be as bleak as it's currently being painted. My hope is that young people will stay connected and get creative. I have no doubt we'll see a sharp rise in entrepreneurship and businesses started by Gen Z, as they take their futures into their own hands.

Alex Goat, Chief Executive of Livity, youth marketing Agency.

The logo for Livity, featuring the word "LIVITY" in a bold, white, sans-serif font centered within a solid black rectangular box.

Summary results

This report covers ten questions which the participants responded. Below, you will find a summary of these responses.

TEN QUESTIONS WE ASKED:

1. Do you think the voice of your generation has been heard in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic?	Majority of the respondents (71%) felt their voices are not heard.
2. COVID-19 is a global event, has it made you more or less concerned about the wellbeing of people in poorer countries?	While most of the respondents indicated they are more concerned or significantly more concerned, a small percentage (15%) indicated they are less concerned.
3. Compared to before the pandemic have your emotional responses during periods of lockdowns and restrictions changed?	The respondents generally reported an increase in eight emotional responses which include boredom, demotivation, loneliness, anxiety, depression, confusion, anger, and fear.
4. Do you feel you and your friends have had access to the support you need?	50% of the respondents feel they do not have access to the necessary support, while 28% indicated the opposite. However, 22% are unsure.
5. Do you agree that companies should employ public health experts for the wellbeing of their employees?	A large majority agree that public health experts should be employed to aid employee wellbeing.
6. Which of these areas do you think large private sector companies should invest in supporting initiatives for the broader societal benefit?	Out of nine options, all the respondents focused on public health. For those that chose to add an option that was not in the list, most indicated a climate-related area of focus.
7. Do you believe public health modules should be incorporated into more university courses?	The respondents were generally in support of public health modules being taught more or being a part of all degrees.
8. Concerning COVID-19, how much do you trust what you read and see in the media and on social media?	The respondents reported on their level of trust across five social media and five news media sources which include Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, Tik Tok, BBC, Guardian, The Sun, The Daily Mail, and The Times. The BBC was the most trusted source and the Sun was the least trusted.
9. Is misinformation a critical challenge today?	The majority (78%) strongly agreed misinformation is a critical challenge.
10. If Public Health England and the UK Government approved a vaccine, would you take this vaccine?	Overall, most respondents said they would take the vaccine; however, almost a fifth said they would not. The responses also differed within the ethnicities.
11. Do you believe there is a need for our digital public health charity?	72% of respondents affirmed, yes there is a need for Cov360. 23% answered maybe, and only 5% said no. The most positive responses came from females, and those of Black and Black British heritage.

Mental Health

“

I believe the pandemic has made people more aware of their mental health. Hopefully, this greater international focus will reduce stigmatisation and facilitate investment in mental health services.

Vlada Shevelkova, 21, postgraduate in Public Health, University of Cambridge.

The new coronavirus has significantly impacted mental health in society. COVID-19, which necessitates self-isolation and social distancing, has led to increased levels of anxiety and stress across society. In addition to exacerbating existing mental health concerns, there is added pressure to rapidly adapt to changing situations and circumstances including social restrictions, school closures, job insecurity, and studying and working from home.

RESULTS FROM SURVEY

Changes in emotional responses during the pandemic

It is evident from Figure 1 that respondents felt their levels of loneliness increased alongside anxiety and depression. Self-isolation and social seclusion are harmful to mental and physical health. They can increase the risk of premature mortality, and the magnitude of risk exceeds that of many leading health indicators. (Novotney, 2019). Demotivation, boredom, anger, and fear have also significantly increased. Reasons for these emotional responses are not apparent without further qualitative

Figure 1. Compared to before the pandemic, have your emotional responses during periods of lockdowns and restriction changed?

A LACK OF SUPPORT

Do you feel you and your friends have had access to the support you need?

50% responded negatively when asked if they felt they had access to mental support while 28% positively and 22% were unsure. Hence, it is crucial for policymakers and government officials to implement mental health support interventions in local communities (Townsend, 2020). In addition, it is important to ensure awareness of existing resources for support.

The voice of those not heard

This question is key to determining an effective solution as it seeks to determine whether the views of those affected are accounted for. A concerning 71% of the respondents felt their voices are not heard, 14% felt that they are heard and 15% are unsure.

As shown in Figure 2, over 70% of women felt they were unheard in comparison to over 50% of men. Researchers claim that women are taking the pandemic more seriously than men. That they are following safety measures more seriously, comply with the pandemic's restrictions better, and are more cautious - taking care of their families. This implies that policy makers must design a gender-differentiated approach to encourage men in society to take mitigation efforts more seriously

(Pietrangelo, 2020). This rationale for why women may feel more unheard could be examined in a qualitative study.

Figure 2. Do you think the voice of your generation has been heard in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic?

Education & Employment

“Public Health Education plays an important role in improving the quality of life within a community.

Toby Goodwin, 23, Physics with Sports Science graduate, Loughborough University.

The pandemic has disrupted the lives of young people, it has affected education and employment. It has revealed considerable disparity between those who can and those who cannot access education. Career prospects for future generations are less promising (DJFY, 2020). Our survey results highlight a compelling case for change. So that employers, including the private sector invest more in public health, introduce public health officers and that there is an increase public health knowledge within the tertiary education sector.

WHERE TO GIVE BACK TO SOCIETY	
Mental health services	21%
1% or more of profits allocated to support poorer communities	18%
Sponsorship to support student studies	13%
Pay staff to spend working time giving back to the community	11%
Medical research	10%
Public health charities	7%
Investment in migrant and refugee health services	7%
Rehabilitation and health support for prison populations	6%
Other	5%
I don't think they need to invest in society any more	2%

These findings indicate that these particular respondents are generally concerned about inequalities and social inequities within the sphere of employment and education. Moreover, they provide a useful indication where large companies can support wellbeing to foster creating shared value in broader society.

The 2% that chose to include a missing option indicated a climate-related area of focus.

In a separate question within the survey, which concerned empathy at an international level, we asked participants to respond to the question: 'COVID-19 is a global event, has it made you more or less concerned about the wellbeing of people in poorer countries?'. Almost half (48%) indicated they are significantly more concerned. Further, 37% advised they are more concerned. While 11% said they are less concerned, only 4% indicated they are significantly less concerned.

Figure 3. Which of these areas do you think large private sector companies should invest in supporting initiatives for broader societal benefit?

THE RISE OF THE PUBLIC HEALTH OFFICER

Do you believe that companies should employ public health experts for the wellbeing of their employees?

A large number of responses agree (41%) or strongly agree (46%) that companies should employ public health experts to provide in-house public health expertise. 11% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed. This highlights a key role employers can play during the onset of epidemics or other health crises, particularly in mitigating avoidable effects and providing employees with relevant information. For such a strategy to be effective, the role of prospective company public health officers or consultants should be clearly defined.

One new trend which has arisen from the pandemic is the need for more expertise and education concerning public health. Indeed, we believe this requires further research and analysis. It could play a pivotal role in the coming years to improve containment concerning infectious diseases and improve individual and collective well-being across a range of social determinants that make up health.

PUBLIC HEALTH EDUCATION FOR ALL

Do you believe public health modules should be incorporated into more university courses?

48% of the respondents said university courses must include more public health modules and 27% want public health modules included in all degree courses. 11% thought that there are enough public health modules taught, and 1% said that these modules should be taught less. The remaining respondents (13%) were unsure. Public health modules are available under the umbrella of preventative medicine. Overall, the responses suggest these modules should be made more widely available.

Figure 4. Do you believe public health modules should be incorporated into more university courses?

Based on Figure 4, the respondents with from Psychology/Marketing disciplines showed the greatest interest in public health modules, which may indicate they felt they had the least understanding of public health. In contrast, a greater percentage from the STEM group felt that there were enough public health modules taught. This shows that the pandemic has exposed the knowledge gap in the current education system.

As an extension of our initial question, and in relation to the responses we received it is pertinent to ask: “If public health information was accessible on a transdisciplinary scale, would society have a higher level of preparedness?”

Misinformation & the Vaccine

“

In my experience working with younger members of Generation Z, I have witnessed an alarming lack of trust of news sources regarding the pandemic. This contributes to students' increased anxiety and uncertainty about their futures.

Tashi Zaffke, 21.

History Graduate from Kings College London, and Trainee teacher in Exeter.

Combating false news and misleading information about COVID-19 is one of the major challenges facing strategies to mitigate, adapt, and recover from the current pandemic. The quality of reportage in widely used news sources and social media need to be assessed. This section explores the participants' assessment of the level misinformation and vaccine confidence.

Findings

- The BBC is the most trusted and the Sun is the least trusted news source.
- LinkedIn is the most trusted social media channel while TikTok is highly untrusted concerning information about the COVID-19 pandemic

THE CHALLENGE OF MISINFORMATION

Is misinformation a critical challenge today?

78% of the respondents agree strongly that misinformation is a challenge while 18% respondents agree, 3% disagreed, and 1% disagreed strongly. This indicates a general awareness that information portrayed on certain mass media platforms is questionable to an extent. It is essential to ensure legitimate sources are available to prevent misleading information from spreading and compromising public health.

Figure 5. How much do you trust what you read and see on the following media concerning COVID-19?

THE MOST TRUSTED MEDIA

Figure 5 shows that the respondents trusted the BBC the most and the Sun the least. It is interesting to note that LinkedIn is the most trusted social media channel. The lower levels of trust in social media platforms indicates the needs for public health information-related regulations to be established for information circulating on such media.

THE VACCINE

If Public Health England and the UK Government approved a vaccine, would you take this vaccine?

53% of the respondents said they would take the vaccine, while 21% said they would not and 26% were unsure. In another survey by Ipsos Mori (2020), 77% of the respondents indicated the popular motive behind the decision to take the vaccine is to protect others from catching the coronavirus. However, the least motivating argument was trust in the government recommending it. The results from Ipsos survey provide an insight into the low levels of vaccine confidence among the respondents of our survey.

Given how the virus appears to be affecting Black and Asian communities, it is important to include a diversity scale across various ethnic backgrounds. Our study was not able to capture this detail.

Figure 6. Cross-tabulated data. Ethnicity vs. If Public Health England and the UK Government approved a vaccine, would you take this vaccine?

As shown in Figure 6, the Black or Black British group is least confident in taking the vaccine followed by the Asian or Asian British group. The White, Mixed and Other ethnic groups are significantly more confident. This indicates an apparent disparity between the various ethnic groups in understanding the COVID-19 vaccine. It is also noteworthy that 57% of male respondents answered positively against 49% of females.

The variance among demographic groups reflects recent polling among commissioned by The Royal Society for Public Health, which indicated among vaccine confidence is lower among black and minority ethnic populations (57% were likely to accept a COVID-19 vaccine, compared to 79% of White respondents). The same poll also showed woman is less likely to get a vaccine jab than men (73% vs 80%) (2020).

To understand the link between misinformation and vaccine confidence, it is useful to consider the controversy surrounding the Measles, Mumps and Rubella (MMR) vaccine and autism. A hypothesised link between the two was a major public health issue that brought to light the influence of misinformation on public opinion regarding vaccination (Burgess, Burgess and Leask, 2006). Myths and misleading facts circulating on media greatly affect vaccine coverage and it is imperative to mitigate them during the pandemic for a quick and effective recovery. The challenge here is to ensure information broadcast about the vaccine is inclusive of all ethnic backgrounds and located within their socio-cultural knowledge in order to increase trust levels.

“The report evidences an endemic failure of trust and communication between public health authorities, education, and the emerging generations burdened with navigating a world of increasingly likely health emergencies.

Josh Entsminger, PhD Candidate UCL IIPP on AI Innovation Ecosystems, and Harvard Extension School Teaching Fellow.

Final thoughts

To conclude our analysis, we offer critical reflections on what Gen Z thinks on the key issues raised in our survey.

MENTAL WELLBEING

The socio-economic effects of the coronavirus have had a profound impact on the overall mental wellbeing of youth in the UK. The study shows that the mitigation measures introduced due to the coronavirus have negatively affected the mental wellbeing of Gen Z.

There is a need for further research on how to support young people in managing well-being. Indeed, it may be prudent to combine this with cross-sectoral investment in education and in mental health services.

EDUCATION & EMPLOYMENT

Where education and employment are concerned, two progressive ideas were elicited:

a. On education, the respondents felt public health modules should be included in their education. This can be addressed by providing the option of selecting from a range of public health modules as general electives or minor subjects.

b. On employment, the respondents supported the inclusion of public health professionals in workplaces. This would also be advantageous to employers, as professionals trained in public health would contribute to the improved wellbeing of their employees. Simultaneously, this could lead to more people employed in such roles, contributing to an improved economic and social infrastructure.

MISINFORMATION & THE VACCINE

Misinformation is regarded as a critical issue. It was insightful to learn which news agencies and social media were most and least trusted. As the vaccine is studied and distributed, news agencies and social media are crucial for establishing trust in the vaccine to ensure uptake. The results show that Gen Z is willing to take the vaccine to protect the general population.

The survey revealed critical points for intervention and a progressive mind-set towards public health. The issues include: developing communication networks so that insights into public health are circulated more widely to address ongoing mental health concerns; integrating preventative medicine and public health knowledge across degrees and ensuring that employers and companies understand and consider investment opportunities that help society and communities to adapt and build back better. And that, media outlets and social media reconsider their approaches to combating misinformation and address the low levels of vaccine confidence that impede efforts to contain, control, mitigate, and eliminate the spread of COVID-19.

Further research

The vaccine is one of the tactics introduced to contain and eliminate the spread of the disease. However, as population immunity level is still unknown, there is an imperative to broaden the strategy to combat the pandemic, and to help Gen Z and the wider society, adapt to the stark circumstances we individually and collectively find ourselves. A holistic approach that improves health outcomes across the areas covered in this report, could not only have a substantial impact on wellbeing in society in general, but also harness the virus. We therefore recommend the following:

First, collecting a larger data sample size would allow for more in depth analysis of the Gen-Z graduate community. Therefore further quantitative research and analysis would be beneficial.

Second, this report covers a range of topics and consequent results that warrant more in depth examination. A further qualitative study would provide greater insight into the results and greater understanding about how to tackle the concerns raised.

Cov360 have identified four areas where programmes need to be developed to catalyse engagement, provide further analysis, and address the concerns raise. These include:

Mental health Further analysis of trends relating to mental health among young people and an initiative, led by young people, to empower and promote mental wellbeing among their peers.	Public health and education A research project that designs and integrates a public health program into the university, college, secondary and primary syllabus and then evaluates what effects this is having.
Public health and employment Collaborative research, training and policies designed to help employers understand what they can do to improve the wellbeing of their staff as well as the broader society's individual and collective wellbeing.	Gen-Z misinformation project Due to concerns raised about the low levels of vaccine confidence and media and social media distrust, the need to invest in a project that supports Gen-Z in their effort to combat false news.

Across these four areas, we believe that it is important to develop a more self-determining, emancipatory approach to promote young people's wellbeing. We recommend further qualitative research to provide a platform for vulnerable communities, so that they are encouraged to voice their perspectives. This in turn will provide greater insight into how their concerns and circumstances can be better addressed. This further study would complement the need to implement inclusive approaches to training and education in public health.

Citations

Royal Society of Public Health, 2020. New poll finds BAME groups less likely to want COVID vaccine. RSPH.
Novotney, A. 2019. 'The risks of social isolation'. American Psychological Association.

Townsend, E. 2020. 'COVID-19 policies in the UK and consequences for mental health'. The Lancet.

Pietrangelo, A. 2020. 'Why Women Are Taking the COVID-19 Pandemic More Seriously Than Men'. Healthline.

Decent Jobs for Youth, 2020. 'Youth and covid-19: impacts on jobs, education, rights and mental well-being'.
International Labour Organisation.

Gebbie, K. Rosenstock, L. Hernandez, LM. 2003. '5. The Need for Public Health Education in Other Programs and
Schools'. Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Educating Public Health Professionals for the 21st Century

World Health Organization. 2020. 'Module 6: Communication'. IMPACT OF RUMOURS AND CRISES. WHO Vaccine
Safety Basics.

Ipsos Mori. 2020. 'Arguments for and against taking a coronavirus vaccine'. Guardian graphic.

This research was conducted based on a partnership between Cov360 - a public health charity, and Debut.

The analysis for and writing of this report were undertaken by Theo Richardson-Gool and Samia Khan. The editors Alicia Ramos and Sofia Chanda.

The design was developed by Jakia Siddique Sufian.

Members of the Cov360 community consulted in the production of the survey and the report include Alex Erquircia, Jade Robinson, Jessie Karlovich, Jonathan Zhang, Josh Entsminger, Tremayne Beckford, and Viktoria Roussina.

From Debut, we thank Kim Connor Streich and Avantika Vaishnav for their input and support.

To be cited as:

Khan., S. Richardson-Gool., T. (2021) Voice of the future. Listening to Gen Z on COVID-19, mental health, education, work, and misinformation, London: Cov360 & Debut.

"For a generation whose most formative years are being shaped by the instability and isolation of the COVID-19 pandemic, this report highlights pressing concerns for mental health and wellbeing, as well as the need for greater education, support and engagement with youth to determine the future of public health."

Zoë Stockton, 23, Human Sciences graduate, University of Oxford.

"Voice of the Future" shows very well the increasing importance of mental wellbeing for the youth. Taking into consideration our concerns is crucial for effective policymaking and strengthening a more resilient future society."

Marina Navarro Montilla, President of the European Student Think Tank.

